

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 139

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 139

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 139:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	
<p>Psa. 139:1 O LORD, You have ^asearched me and known <i>me</i>. ² You ^aknow ¹when I sit down and ²when I rise up; You ^bunderstand my thought from afar. ³ You ^{1a}scrutinize my ²path and my lying down, And are intimately acquainted with all my ways. ⁴ ¹Even before there is a word on my tongue, Behold, O LORD, You ^aknow it all. ⁵ You have ^aenclosed me behind and before, And ^blaid Your hand upon me. ⁶ <i>Such</i> ^aknowledge is ^btoo wonderful for me; It is <i>too</i> high, I cannot attain to it.</p>	<p>Psa. 139:1 לְמִנְצַחַת לְדָוִד מִזְמוֹר יְהוָה חִקְרָתָנִי וַתֵּדַע : ² אֵתָה יְדַעַת שְׁבֹתַי וְקוּמִי בְּנִתָּה לְרַעִי מִרְחֹק : ³ אָרְתִי וְרַבְעִי זָרִית וְכָל־דְּרָכַי הִסְכַּנְתָּה : ⁴ כִּי אֵין מַלְּה בְּלִשׁוֹנִי תֵּן יְהוָה יְדַעַת כְּלָה : ⁵ אַחֲזֹר וְנִקְדָּם צִרְתָּנִי וַתִּשָּׂא עָלַי כַּפְּכָה : ⁶ בְּלֵאִיָּה [פְּלִיאָה] דַּעַת מִמֶּנִּי נִשְׁנָבָה לֹא־אוּכַל לָהּ : ⁷ אֵאָנָה אֵלֶיךָ מִרוּחֶךָ וְאֵאָנָה מִפְּנֵיךָ אֲבָרַח : ⁸ אִם־אֶסְק שָׁמַיִם שָׁם אֵתָה וְאֶצִּיעָה שָׂאוֹל תִּנְדָּךְ : ⁹ אֵשָׂא כַּנְפֵי־שָׁחַר אֲשַׁכְּנָה בְּאַחֲרֵית יָם : ¹⁰ גַּם־שָׁם יְדַךְ תִּנְחַנֵּי וְתִאֲחַזְנֵי יְמִינֶךָ : ¹¹ וְאָמַר אֶךְ־חֲשֹׁךְ יִשׁוּפְנִי וְלִילָה אֲזוֹר בְּעַדְנִי : ¹² גַּם־חֲשֹׁךְ לֹא־יִתְּשִׁיךְ לְמַךְ וְלִילָה כִּי־יֵאִיר כַּחֲשִׁיכָה כָּאוֹרָה : ¹³ כִּי־אֵתָה קִנִּיתָ כְּלִיָּתִי תִּסְכְּנֵי בְּבֶטֶן אִמִּי : ¹⁴ אֲזוֹדֶךָ עַל כִּי נֹדַרְתָּ נִפְלִיתִי נִפְלְאִים מַעֲשֵׂיךָ וְנִבְשִׁי יְדַעַת מְאֹד : ¹⁵ לֹא־נִכְחַד עֲצָמִי לְמַךְ אֲשֶׁר־עָשִׂיתִי בַסֶּתֶר וְקִמְתִּי בְּתַחְתֵּי־אָרֶץ : ¹⁶ גַּלְמִי רָאוּ עֵינֶיךָ וְעַל־סִבְרֶךָ כָּל־</p>

¹⁰ Even there Your hand will ^alead me,

And Your right hand will lay hold of me.

¹¹ If I say, “Surely the ^adarkness will ¹overwhelm me,

And the light around me will be night,”

¹² Even the ^adarkness is not dark ¹to You,

And the night is as bright as the day.

^bDarkness and light are alike *to You*.

Psa. 139:13 For You ^aformed my ¹inward parts;

You ^bwove me in my mother’s womb.

¹⁴ I will give thanks to You, for ¹I am fearfully and wonderfully made;

^aWonderful are Your works,

And my soul knows it very well.

¹⁵ My ^{1a}frame was not hidden from You,

When I was made in secret,

And skillfully wrought in the ^bdepths of the earth;

¹⁶ Your ^aeyes have seen my unformed substance;

And in ^bYour book were all written

The ^cdays that were ordained *for me*,

When as yet there was not one of them.

Psa. 139:17 How precious also are Your ^athoughts to me, O God!

How vast is the sum of them!

¹⁸ If I should count them, they would ^aoutnumber the sand.

When ^bI awake, I am still with You.

וְכָתְבוּ יָמַי יְצִרְוּ וְלֹא [וְ] [לֹא]

אֶחָד בָּהֶם : ¹⁷ וְלִי מִה־יִקְרָו רַעִיד

אֵל מִה עֲצֻמוֹ רְאִשֵׁיהֶם : ¹⁸ אֶסְפְּרֵם

מִחֹל יִרְבּוֹן הַקִּיצֹתַי וְעוֹדֵי עִמּוּד :

¹⁹ אִם־תִּקְטֹל אֱלֹהִים אֶרְשָׁע וְאֲנִשִּׁי

דָּמַיִם סוּרוֹ מִנִּי : ²⁰ אֲשֶׁר יֹאמְרוּךְ

לְמִזְמֵה נָשָׂא לְשׂוֹא עָרִיד : ²¹

הֲלוֹא־מִשְׁנֵאֵיךְ יִתְנֶה אֶשְׁנֵא

וּבִתְקוּמָיִךְ אֶתְקוּטֵט : ²² תִּכְלִית

שְׁנֵאָה שְׁנֵאָתַיִם לְאוֹיְבַיִם הִיוּ לִי : ²³

חֲקַרְנִי אֵל וְרַע לְבָבִי בְחַזְנִי וְרַע

שָׂרְעִפִי : ²⁴ וְרָאָה אִם־הֲרָךְ־עֵצֶב

בִּי וְנִחַנִּי בְּרָךְ עוֹלָם :

Psa. 139:19 O that You would
"slay the wicked, O God;

^bDepart from me, therefore, 'men
of bloodshed.

²⁰ For they "speak ¹against You
wickedly,

And Your enemies ^{2b}take *Your name*
in vain.

²¹ Do I not "hate those who hate
You, O LORD?

And do I not ^bloathe those who
rise up against You?

²² I hate them with the utmost
hatred;

They have become my enemies.

Psa. 139:23 "Search me, O God,
and know my heart;

^bTry me and know my anxious
thoughts;

²⁴ And see if there be any ^{1a}hurtful
way in me,

And ^blead me in the 'everlasting
way.

References

Psalm 139:1

^aPs 17:3; 44:21; Jer 12:3

Psalm 139:2

¹Lit *my sitting*

²Lit *my rising*

^a2 Kin 19:27

^bPs 94:11; Is 66:18; Matt 9:4

Psalm 139:3

¹Lit *winnow*

²Or *journeying*

^aJob 14:16; 31:4

Psalm 139:4

¹Lit *For there is not*

^aHeb 4:13

Psalm 139:5

^aPs 34:7; 125:2

^bJob 9:33

Psalm 139:6

^aRom 11:33

^bJob 42:3

Psalm 139:7

^aJer 23:24

Psalm 139:8

¹I.e. the nether world

^aAmos 9:2-4

^bJob 26:6; Prov 15:11

Psalm 139:10

^aPs 23:2, 3

Psalm 139:11

¹Lit *bruise*; some commentators read *cover*
^aJob 22:13

Psalm 139:12

¹Lit *from*
^aJob 34:22; Dan 2:22
^{b1}John 1:5

Psalm 139:13

¹Lit *kidneys*
^aPs 119:73; Is 44:24
^bJob 10:11

Psalm 139:14

¹Some ancient versions read *You are fearfully wonderful*
^aPs 40:5

Psalm 139:15

¹Lit *bones were*
^aJob 10:8-10; Eccl 11:5
^bPs 63:9

Psalm 139:16

^aJob 10:8-10; Eccl 11:5
^bPs 56:8
^cJob 14:5

Psalm 139:17

^aPs 40:5; 92:5

Psalm 139:18

^aPs 40:5
^bPs 3:5

Psalm 139:19

^aIs 11:4
^bPs 6:8; 119:115
^cPs 5:6; 26:9

Psalm 139:20

¹Or *of*

²Some mss read *lift themselves up* against You

^aJude 15

^bEx 20:7; Deut 5:11

Psalm 139:21

^a2 Chr 19:2; Ps 26:5; 31:6

^bPs 119:158

Psalm 139:23

^aJob 31:6; Ps 26:2

^bPs 7:9; Prov 17:3; Jer 11:20; 1 Thess 2:4

Psalm 139:24

¹Lit *way of pain*

^aPs 146:9; Prov 15:9; 28:10; Jer 25:5; 36:3

^bPs 5:8; 143:10

^cPs 16:11

Targum

Psa. 139:1 For praise, composed by David, a psalm. O LORD, you have searched me out and known me. ² It is manifest before you when I sit down to study the Torah, and when I rise up to go to war; you understand my fellowship in your congregation from a people afar off. ³ Now when I walk in the road or when I recline to study the Torah, you have become a stranger; and you have made all my ways dangerous. ⁴ And when there is no speech on my tongue, behold, O LORD, you know the thought of my heart completely. ⁵ From behind me and in front of me you have confined me, and you have inflicted on me the blow of your hand. ⁶ It is hidden from my knowing; it is too mighty, I am not capable of it. ⁷ Where will I go from the presence of your storm-wind? And where shall I flee from your presence? ⁸ If I go up to the heavens, you are there; and if I lower myself to Sheol, behold, there is your word. ⁹ I will lift up the fringes of sunrise, I will abide at the ends of the sea. ¹⁰ Also there your hand will guide me, and your right hand will seize me. ¹¹ And I said, “Truly, darkness will blind me, and the night will become dark for my sake.” ¹² Also the darkness will not be too dark for your word, and the night, like day, will give light; like darkness, like light – they are equal. ¹³ For you have created my kidneys; you established me in the belly of my mother. ¹⁴ I will give you thanks, for you have miraculously done awesome things; your works are wonderful, and my soul knows it well. ¹⁵ My self is not hidden from you, for I was made in secret, I was formed in the belly of my mother. ¹⁶ Your eyes see my body; and in the book of your remembrance all my days were written on the day the world was created; in the beginning all creatures were created but not on a single day among them. ¹⁷ And how precious to me are those who love you, the righteous, O God; and how mighty have their scholars become! ¹⁸ I will number them in this age: they will be more numerous than sand; I awake in the age to come and still I am with you. ¹⁹ If you slay, O God, the wicked man, [then] men who are worthy of the judgment of death will depart from me. ²⁰ Who will swear in your name for deception, taking an oath in vain, your enemies. ²¹ Do I not hate all those who hate you, O LORD? And when they rise against you, I am incensed. ²² I hate them to the destruction of hatred; they have become enemies to me. ²³ Search me out, O God, and know my thoughts; examine me and know my thinking. ²⁴ And see if any way of error is in me; and guide me in the path of those eternally upright.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The sage Ibn Ezra described this Psalm as an extraordinary lesson on the ways of the LORD. This is the only Psalm which examines the roots and reasons for creation so intimately. As every new generation enters their stage of history, it follows an ancient script, and a predetermined Divine drama unfolds. Humanity was freewill to choose which direction it will go. This is a paradox that the rabbis have debated for centuries. If freewill exists, then a predetermined drama cannot exist. Only the LORD can explain how these two items are in balance.

Superscript

The author calls upon the Sefirah Netzach for victory.

To Him who grants victory, by David, a psalm.

Notes on this Psalm

Predetermination is an interesting topic to discuss. On one hand, if this exists then humanity is a puppet of the LORD as He pulls the strings. Freewill allows humanity to create its own destiny. This paradox is debated in many writings and has been debated by sages and rabbis. Does the LORD influence daily life on Earth? There are people who believe that the LORD created the Earth and humanity but then left to watch what would happen. A problem with this idea is that it is clear there are historical events where the LORD has stepped in. For example, the LORD's work was seen at the Exodus and the Red Sea. The LORD became known to Israel when it camped at the base of Mount Sinai. There is a Midrash that says that the LORD allowed Adam to see the future. Adam saw what was to happen to King David and

gave him 25 years of his life. Adam lived to 975 years instead of 1000 years. This Midrash comes out on the side of predetermination. But if this exists, then why would the LORD allow the sins that caused the destruction of the Temple to occur? Certainly, the LORD would have been able to stop that from happening.

This debate will continue through the centuries until humanity dies out. This is a secret of existence that one will discover the answer to when one returns to the Lower Waters of Heaven. Perhaps we will discover that the LORD's system was to allow freewill that would not affect the Divine history of humanity.

Appendix

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Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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